

The Identification of Adverse Events by Applying “Global Trigger Tool” In Indoor Patients of a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital

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ABSTRACT

Background: Adverse events (AEs) in hospitalized patients are a significant concern for patient safety. Traditional detection methods often underreport such events. This study evaluates the effectiveness of the IHI GTT in identifying AEs across multiple departments in a tertiary care teaching hospital. **Methods:** A prospective observational study was conducted over 11 months (December 2022 – November 2023) across five departments: Medicine, Surgery, Orthopaedics, OBGY, and ICU. Adult inpatients (≥ 18 years) with hospital stays >24 hours were included. Patient records were reviewed using the IHI GTT, and identified AEs were validated and categorized using the NCC MERP Index. **Results:** Among 220 patients, 200 (90.9%) had at least one trigger, and 47 AEs were identified in 41 patients (18.6%). Medication-related triggers were most common (61.18%), followed by care-related (25.77%) and surgical triggers (5.09%). The overall AE rate was 21.36 per 100 patients. Most AEs (68%) occurred within the first 10 days of hospitalization. The highest AE rates were observed in the Orthopaedics and Medicine departments. The tool demonstrated high sensitivity (100%) but low specificity (11.17%). **Conclusion:** The IHI GTT is a sensitive method for detecting AEs in hospitalized patients, particularly medication-related events. Its implementation can enhance patient safety monitoring and support pharmacovigilance efforts. However, refinement is needed to improve specificity and reduce false positives.

Keywords: Global trigger tool, adverse event, IHI

INTRODUCTION

First, Do no harm has been the founding principle of medical practice since the days of Hippocrates.^[1] Traditionally, adverse events detection relied on voluntary reporting and tracking of errors. To effectively address patient safety, hospitals need a more efficient method for identifying and evaluating harmful events.^[2] The Global Trigger Tool (GTT), an active monitoring tool launched by the Institute for Health Care Improvement (IHI) in 2003 and revised in 2009, is able to detect medically related adverse events with six modules of “care”, “medication”, “surgical”, “intensive care”, “perinatal”, and “emergency”.^[2] Compared with the spontaneous reporting system (SRS) and adverse event medical record review, GTT purposefully locates AEs-related content, thereby improving the efficiency and accuracy of case review.^[3]

The Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI) trigger tool is a low-cost, low-tech method for detecting adverse events and adverse reactions through clues (triggers) such as: the use of antidotes, antiemetics, variations in relevant laboratory tests such as the prothrombin time, INR (international normalized ratio), serum creatinine, glucose, plasma levels of low therapeutic index drugs (phenytoin, warfarin, methotrexate, etc.). This technique seems to increase the detection rate of adverse events by a factor of approximately 50 compared to traditional methodologies.^[4]

While previous studies have primarily relied on retrospective record review, our approach incorporates prospective surveillance to refine the application of trigger tools and identify real-time factors contributing to adverse drug reactions (ADRs). By randomly selecting and analysing patient

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records, including multiple departments, we aim to foster a culture of safety that prioritizes system redesign over individual blame.^[3]

Ultimately, our goal is to assess the feasibility and potential of the Global Trigger Tool (GTT) for identifying adverse events (AEs) in different departments/specialities in a tertiary care teaching hospital.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This prospective observational study was conducted for the duration of 11 months from December 2022 to November 2023, by reviewing 'in-door patient records' of medicine (4 months), surgery (2 months), orthopedic (1 month), OBGY (2 months) and intensive care units (2 months) of tertiary care teaching hospital. This study included records of patient aged ≥ 18 years patients with hospital stay > 24 hours and excluded inpatient psychiatric & rehabilitation patients. Study was approved by Institutional Ethics Committee (PDUMCR/IEC/38/2022) Dated: 30/11/2022.

➤ Study methodology:

Patient's records were randomly selected every two weeks in each department, with 10 patients between 1st and 15th of the month for the first two-week sample and between 16th and end of the month for the second two-week sample on the day of admission. Thus, there were 20 records per month per department.

Written informed consent (≥ 18 years) was obtained before collecting demographic & clinical information from patients at the point of care. Patients were evaluated for triggers and AEs until discharge.

Reviewing methodology: The IHI Global Trigger tool was used for reviewing patients' records. A team of three reviewers independently reviewed all records. If a trigger is identified in a record it indicates a positive trigger and the reviewer reviews the record to identify whether an AEs has occurred or not. "Positive trigger" does not necessarily means an adverse event. If any

adverse event is identified, the treating physician first authenticates and the AE is then categorized according to National Coordinating Council for Medication Error Reporting and Prevention (NCC MERP) Index. ^[5]

➤ STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

All data were analyzed using Microsoft excel 2013. Descriptive statistics and accuracy measures were used for detailed analysis.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

This observational, prospective study was carried out to assess the feasibility and potential of the global trigger tool for identifying adverse events (AEs) in different departments of a tertiary care teaching hospital. A total of 220 records of patients fulfilling the selection criteria were enrolled. Female: male ratio was 1.2:1 (Female [54.54%] and male [45.45%]). The age ranged from 18 to 90 years with the mean age of 41.98 years \pm 19.96 SD. And most of them were in the age group of 18-32 years, which includes 95 patients.

In our study, out of 53 triggers, 20 triggers were found 353 times in 200 patients. Of the 20 triggers, AEs were identified with only 12 triggers. In the remaining 20 patients out of 220, neither a trigger nor an AE was found. Medication (M) module triggers (216 times; 61.18%) were the most commonly observed trigger followed by Care (C) module triggers (91 times; 25.77%), Surgical (S) module triggers (18 times; 5.09%), Perinatal (P) module triggers (17 times; 4.81%) and Intensive care (I) module triggers (11 times, 3.11%).

Positive predictive value (PPV) is defined as the number of times a specific trigger independently identified AEs divided by the number of times a trigger was identified. ^[6] In our study, PPV of 20 triggers were calculated and it was found that PPV for individual triggers ranged from 0% to 100%. Five triggers showed 100% PPV which included triggers C11, S8, S11, M2 and M13. [table 1]

Trigger	No. of times the trigger was detected	No. of times the trigger was associated with AE	PPV (%)

Care (C) module triggers			
C1: Transfusion or use of blood products	59	5	8.47
C2: Code/arrest/rapid response team	-	-	-
C3: Acute dialysis	-	-	-
C4: Positive blood culture	-	-	-
C5: X-ray or Doppler studies for emboli	-	-	-
C6: Decrease of greater than 25% Hb	-	-	-
C7: Patient fall	-	-	-
C8: Pressure ulcers	-	-	-
C9: Readmission within 30 days	6	0	0
C10: Restraint use	-	-	-
C11: Healthcare-associated infection	13	13	100
C12: In- hospital stroke	-	-	-
C13: Transfer to higher level	13	0	0
Surgical (S) module triggers			
S1: Return to surgery	15	3	20
S2: Change in procedure	-	-	-
S3: Admission to intensive care post-op	-	-	-
S4: Intubation	-	-	-
S5: X-ray intra-op or in PACU	-	-	-
S6: Intra-op or post-op death	-	-	-
S7: Mechanical ventilation > 24 hours post-op	-	-	-
S8: Intra-op epinephrine, norepinephrine, naloxone, or Romazicon	2	2	100
S9: Post-op troponin level greater than 1.5 ng/ml	-	-	-
S10: Injury, repair, or removed of organ	-	-	-
S11: Any operative complication	1	1	100
Medication (M) module Triggers			
M1: <i>Clostridium difficile</i> positive stool	-	-	-
M2: Partial thromboplastin time greater than 100 seconds	1	1	100
M3: International Normalized Ratio > 6	-	-	-
M4: Glucose less than 50mg/dl	4	3	75
M5: Rising BUN or serum creatinine greater than 2 times baseline	3	2	66.66
M6: Vitamin K administration	14	4	28.57
M7: Antihistaminic use	30	9	30
M8: Romazicon use	-	-	-
M9: Naloxone use	-	-	-
M10: Anti-emetic use	156	0	0
M11: Over-sedation/hypotension	-	-	-
M12: Abrupt medication stop	5	0	0
M13: Other	3	3	100
Intensive care (I) module triggers			
I1: Pneumonia onset	-	-	-
I2: Readmission to intensive care	-	-	-
I3: In-unit procedure	-	-	-
I4: Intubation/reintubation	11	0	0
Perinatal (P) module triggers			

P1: Terbutaline use	5	0	0
P2: 3 rd or 4 th degree laceration	-	-	-
P3: Platelet count less than 50000	-	-	-
P4: Estimated blood loss >500 ml (vaginal) or >1000 ml (C-section)	1	0	0
P5: Specialty consult	-	-	-
P6: Oxytocic agents	10	1	10
P7: Instrumented delivery	-	-	-
P8: General anaesthesia	1	0	0
Emergency department module triggers			
E1: readmission to ED within 48 hours	-	-	-
E2: Time in ED greater than 6 hours	-	-	-

Sensitivity is the ability to correctly identify true positives and specificity is the ability to correctly identify true negatives.^[7] The IHI GTT had sensitivity of 100%, indicating that all actual adverse events were

detected by the triggers. Specificity was calculated as 11.17%, indicating that a low proportion of non-adverse events were correctly identified by the triggers.

Trigger	Adverse event		Total
	Yes	No	
Yes	41	159	200
No	0	20	20
Total	41	179	220

Total 47 AEs were identified out of which 31 (65.95%) AEs were present on admission and 16 (34.04%) AEs after the admission [Table 3]. Out of total 47 AEs, maximum 21 AEs was identified in medicine department followed by 17 AEs in

orthopedics, 6 AEs in surgery, 2 AEs in OBGY and 1 AEs in ICU. Majority of the adverse events occurred within the first 10 days of stay while with increasing length of stay, the triggers and adverse events both decreased.

Adverse events	Total no. of AEs	Event present on admission? (Yes/No)
Healthcare associated infection	13	Yes
Methotrexate: Drug toxicity	2	Yes
Oral hypoglycaemic agent -Hypoglycaemia	2	Yes
Insulin – Hypoglycaemic Seizure	1	Yes
Operative complication - Enterocutaneous fistula	1	Yes
Operative complication – PPH	1	No
Vancomycin – 1.Red man syndrome 2.Itching 3.Urticaria	3	No
Sodium bicarbonate – Urticaria	1	No
Warfarin – 1.Subdural haemorrhage 2.Subdural hematoma 3.Bleeding 4.Hemetemesis	4	Yes
Acitrom – Bleeding	2	Yes

Azathioprine – Leukopenia	1	Yes
Acyclovir – Burning sensation	1	No
MVI – 1.Allergic reaction 2.Dyspnea	2	No
Bupivacaine – Hypotension	1	No
Propofol & Succinyl choline – Hypotension	1	No
Palbociclib & Fulvestrant – Pancytopenia	1	Yes
Ceftriaxone – Anaphylactic reaction	1	No
Meropenem – Rash	1	No
Calcium gluconate – Rigor	1	No
Colistin – Raised serum creatinine	1	No
Enoxaparin – Purpura	1	No
Blood cell packed human – Hyperkalaemia	1	No
Pyrimethamine-sulphadoxine – Haematuria	1	Yes
Return to Surgery	3	Yes
Total	47	

Majority of the AEs identified was due to medication (drug) related 29 (61.70%) followed by care related 16 (34.04%) and procedure related 2 (4.25%). Care related AEs like post-operative infections were

identified in orthopaedic and surgery department. Two procedure related AEs like PPH and enterocutaneous fistula were identified in OBGY and surgery department respectively. [Table 4] The rate of adverse events (AEs) was 21.36/100 patients.

Table 4: AEs distribution according to type of events	
Type of events	Total no. of AEs (%)
Medication related	29 (61.70%)
Care related	16 (34.04%)
Procedure related	2 (4.25%)
Total	47 100%

The IHI Global Trigger Tool adapts the classification from the **National Coordinating Council for Medication Error Reporting and Prevention (NCC MERP) Index** [5] for Categorizing Errors. The IHI Global Trigger Tool counts only adverse events: harm to the patient, whether or not the result of an error. Accordingly, the tool excludes the categories A, B, C and D from the NCC MERP Index because these

categories describe errors that do not cause harm. This tool utilizes categories E, F, G, H, and I of the NCC MERP Index because these categories describe harm. In our study majority of AEs belongs to “harm category F” (31 AEs) followed by “harm category E” (14 AEs). [Figure 1]

Table 5 shows various measures to analyze the AEs in which orthopedic department reported highest AEs per 1000 patient days (85.43%), AEs per 100 admissions (85%) and 65% of admission with AEs.

Department	Measure 1: AEs per 1000 patient days	Measure 2: AEs per 100 admissions	Measure 3: % of admission with AEs
Orthopaedic	85.43	85%	65%
Surgery	24.1	15%	15%
Medicine	66.25	26.25%	23.75%
OBGY	9.52	5%	5%
Intensive care unit	6.25	2.5%	2.5%

Out of total 220 enrolled patients, 41 AEs detected were associated with triggers but 159 of patients were having triggers but no AEs detected.

Flow chart of adverse events and trigger detection in a indoor patients

4. DISCUSSION

There are several methods to monitor ADRs like voluntary reporting, record review, triggers, direct observation, interviews/surveys, targeted reporting,

cohort event monitoring, electronic health record (HER) mining. [8] Voluntary reporting of ADRs is most commonly used method for reporting of ADRs. [9] However, voluntary reporting has some disadvantages like under reporting, reporting bias,

difficult to detect delayed ADRs and capture only suspected ADRs. So, other methods needed to improve reporting of ADRs^[8] and one of them is trigger tool method. Trigger tools, on the other hand, offer advantages like early detection and the ability to determine incidence rates.^[8] By identifying adverse events using the Global Trigger Tool, we can significantly improve patient safety within the hospital. This proactive approach leads to fewer hospital readmissions, as patients are less likely to experience complications that would necessitate a return to the hospital. Consequently, this reduces the need for additional medications to treat these complications, thereby lowering overall healthcare costs and minimizing patient exposure to drugs. This decreased exposure to medications, in turn, reduces the likelihood of medication-related adverse events, creating a safer healthcare environment and improving patient outcomes. The IHI Global Trigger Tool is a universal tool adopted by researchers worldwide for this purpose.^[8]

Adverse events (AEs) in healthcare settings pose significant challenges to patient safety.^[10] While medication-related adverse reactions have been extensively studied,^[3,4] there are numerous other areas where patient safety can be compromised. This study explores the identification of adverse events beyond medication-related issues using the Global Trigger Tool (GTT) in indoor patients of a tertiary care teaching hospital. In the present study, we included various departments like Orthopaedic, Surgery, Medicine, OBGY and ICU where as in the study done by Menat U et al.^[11] study was done only in medicine department and in another study done by Gohil JP et al.^[12] it was done only in surgery department. In the present study, 43.18% of patients were in the age group of 18-32 years with mean age 41.98 ± 19.96 years while in the study done by Almeida et al.^[4] 55.3% were in the age group of 18-59 years and the mean age of adult patients in the study done by Pandya et al. was 47 ± 14 years.^[13]

Female patients were more (54.54 %) in our study which is similar to the study done by Xu et al.^[14] (62.1%) whereas in another study done by Kurutkan et al.^[15] male patients (51.52%) were more compared to female patients (48.47%). The IHI GTT tool Module comprises of total 53 triggers (IHI

GTT).^[2] We identified 20 triggers occurring 353 times in 200 patients. While study done by Xu et al.^[14] included 51 triggers out of which 26 triggers were found 206 times in 240 patients. However, only 12 out of 20 triggers were identified with AEs. In Xu et al.^[14] study, 17 out of the 51 triggers were associated with AEs. In 20 patients, neither a trigger nor an adverse event was found, which is similar to study by Chan et al.^[16] In the present study, “medication (M) module triggers” (61.18%) were the most frequently observed followed by “care (C) module triggers” (25.77%) and “surgical (S) module triggers” (5.09%). Whereas study done by Xu et al.^[14] care module triggers (38.83%) were most frequently observed followed by medication module triggers (37.37%) and surgical (S) module triggers (14.07%). Several factors could explain this discrepancy. Variations in healthcare practices, hospital protocols, and patient demographics across different regions can impact the frequency and type of triggers identified. Positive Predictive Values (PPVs) are frequently used to assess the efficiency of triggers.^[7] In our study, individual triggers demonstrated PPV ranging from 0% to 100% which is similar to the findings by Nicole et al.^[17] In our study, seven triggers had $PPV \geq 50\%$. Among these five triggers had a 100% PPV, consistently leading to adverse events in every identified case. The high PPV suggests more harm to the patients. Several triggers in our study demonstrated less than 50% PPV and 33 triggers never occurred. Whereas study done by Carnevali et al.^[18] found that 14 triggers had PPVs less than 50% and 3 triggers never occurred. On the other hand, antiemetic which was frequently identified trigger (>100 times) had 0% PPV. This is attributed to the common prescribing habit among health care professionals in our hospital, where antiemetics are routinely prescribed to most of the inpatients, regardless of symptoms without any pharmacological justification. This, in turn, can contribute to many false positive findings. These triggers require further specification to enhance their effectiveness in identifying adverse events.

Sensitivity is the ability to correctly identify true positives and specificity is the ability to correctly identify true negatives.^[7] In our study, the IHI GTT (53 triggers) had a sensitivity of 100%, means it correctly identified all adverse events (AEs) triggered

by the tool. But specificity was low 11.17% (20 out of 179 patients), indicating that a low proportion of non-adverse events were correctly identified by the triggers. Another study done by Matlow et al. [19] reported a sensitivity of 88% and specificity of 44%. The high sensitivity is beneficial for ensuring that adverse events are not missed, but low specificity suggests that the tool may need refinement to reduce the number of false positives. In our study low specificity is because certain triggers, like the use of blood transfusions preoperatively or as a treatment for low haemoglobin levels (anemia), patient transferred to higher-level care due to a lack of available services to treat complicated cases, abrupt discontinuation of medication based on culture sensitivity results or prescriber's choice, the use of terbutaline for preterm labour pain, and the need for intubation often due to a low Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score were identified as better therapeutic option rather than trigger with adverse events. In these scenarios, the presence of a trigger does not necessarily indicate an adverse event. Our study indicates that certain departments, such as Medicine and Orthopaedic, have a higher frequency of adverse events which can be attributed to patient flow, suggesting a need for more careful monitoring or additional safety measures in these departments. Conversely, departments like ICU and OBGY have fewer adverse events, which might suggest limitation of small sample size or different patient risk profiles.

A significant finding from our data is that the majority of adverse events (32 out of total 47) occur within the first 10 days of hospitalization. This could be due to various factors such as the initial treatment phase, patient adjustment to the hospital environment, or the severity of conditions being treated initially. As the length of stay increases, both the number of triggers and adverse events decreases. This might indicate that once patients are stabilized and pass the critical initial phase, the risk of adverse events diminishes. On the contrary, study done by Hwang et al. [20] found that patients with longer stays tends to have more adverse events. One reason for this discrepancy could be the difference in study design. Our study is prospective, allowing for real-time monitoring and identification of adverse events, whereas the study done by Hwang et al. [20] is retrospective, relying on existing records that may contain incomplete or inaccurate

information. Additionally, improper history-taking by healthcare workers at the time of admission in retrospective studies can lead to underreporting of adverse events. Our findings imply that healthcare providers should pay extra attention on patients during the first 10 days of their stay, as they are most susceptible to adverse events during this period. Enhanced monitoring and preventive measures during these critical early days could potentially reduce the number of adverse events. In our study, long term care-related infections were frequently identified as a leading cause of hospital admission, followed by medication-related AEs, most commonly associated with anticoagulant drugs. Notably, the majority (65.95%) of AEs in our study were present on admission, contrasting with the findings of Kennerly et al. [21], who reported that only 37.9% of AEs were present on admission.

Most adverse events (AEs) in our study were present on admission highlighting the critical role of both patient and healthcare provider roles in their occurrence. For example, infections following surgical operations highlight the combined importance of patient adherence to post-operative care instructions and the healthcare providers' role during surgery. Warfarin-induced bleeding underscores the need for frequent monitoring by healthcare providers and patient compliance with dosage schedules. In case with methotrexate toxicity it was observed that often patients mistakenly took overdose, emphasizing the necessity of healthcare providers giving clear instructions and ensuring that patients follow them strictly. [22] Proper education and strict adherence to guidelines by both patients and healthcare providers are essential to reduce the incidence of these events. In the present study, the majority of adverse events were "medication-related" (61.70%), followed by "care-related issues" such as infections (34.04%), and the least were due to "procedure-related issues" (4.25%), whereas in a study done by Najjar et al. [23] reported that "surgical-procedure" related issue as the leading cause (27.5%). Understanding this distribution helps in identifying areas that need more attention to improve patient safety and care quality. Improving patients' safety requires a multifaceted approach, including better infection control, efficient counselling of patients regarding suspected drug adverse effects, [22]

vigilant approach of nursing staff and advocating proper aseptic precaution by the patient after discharge. Most AEs were temporary and required hospitalization(65.95%), while small percentage (2.12%) lead to life sustaining intervention or death.

The present study observed an adverse events rate of 21.36%, which is lower than those reported by Kennerly et al. (38.1%)^[21] and Carnevali et al. (26%)^[18], but higher than Gohil et al. (12.25%)^[24] The Orthopaedic department showed the highest AEs rates, mainly due to postoperative care infection, indicating the need for stringent aseptic precautions. This is in contrast to the study by Rutberg et al.^[25] The medicine department had the second-highest AEs rates, emphasizing the need for close monitoring of drugs having narrow therapeutic index^[26] and the implementation of preventive measures. Surgery, OBGY, and ICU had lower AEs rates, suggesting better management and appropriate counselling in these departments.

CONCLUSION

The IHI Global Trigger Tool (GTT) is effective method for identifying adverse events. Detecting adverse events beyond just medication-related issues can significantly improve the healthcare system and minimize patient harm. Our results showed that 89.16% inpatients had at least one positive trigger, 17% inpatients had AEs. By evaluating all departments, we can identify which department require more attention and implement strategies to reduce adverse events. Utilizing trigger tools not only helps in identifying adverse events but also contributes to increased reporting of adverse drug reactions (ADRs) as part of pharmacovigilance. The triggers established in this study were proven to be more sensitive but less specific in the active monitoring of AEs among inpatients. So, further research is required to explore the feasibility and acceptability of trigger tool.

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